

Code System for Complexity, Accuracy, Communicative Adequacy

Code System	Memo
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Errors	
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Errors\Grammar	<p>Definition: This code is assigned to deviations from morphological or syntactical norms. Deviations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • errors in the word structure (e.g., incorrect plural form, incorrect verb number/tense/aspect/mood, omission of third person singular -s) • errors in structures at the phrase and clause level (e.g., omission of words, superfluous words, incorrect use of <i>a/an</i>, word disorder, omission of subject-verb inversion or dummy <i>do</i> in interrogative sentences). <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For errors at the word level, the code is assigned to the entire word. • For incorrect verb forms (e.g., tense, aspect), code the element that contains the error, e.g., "<u>Did</u> you have a room...". • For omission of dummy <i>do</i> in interrogatives, assign the code to the main verb, e.g., "How much space <u>has</u> it". • When present continuous instead of present simple is used, assign the code to the gerund verb [<i>-ing</i> form], e.g., "Is that <u>working</u>?". • For word disorder, code the word(s) or group of words that would need to be rearranged in order to correct the utterance with minimal changes, e.g., "In which room can i <u>make also</u> private speaks" <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ For missing words, code the subsequent word, e.g., "I am searching <u>a</u> room". ○ For missing elements at the end of a sentence, code the final word of the sentence. ○ For superfluous words, code the word or words that would need to be removed in order to correct the utterance with minimal changes, e.g., "it<u>s</u> also must be posible" • When a lexical item contains a lexical error as well as a spelling and/or grammatical error, assign error code "lexis" only, e.g. "Can we <u>made</u> a Presentation [lexical error/not coded for "grammar"]". <p>Do NOT code as "error":</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "150 persons"

- "I'm working for the company..."
- "in room Alpha", "in the Alpha room" (but not: "in the room Alpha" > grammatical error)
- "wanna", "gonna" etc.
- "minimum 150 people" / "maximum 1500 Francs"
- questions/negations with "have got", e.g., "How much space has it got?"
- Dates:
 - **Code as "error":**
"on 12 October 2019"; "on 12th October 2019"; "on the 12th of October 2019"; "on 12/10/2019"; "on 12.10.2019"; "on 12-10-2019"; "on October 12th, 2019"; "on October 12, 2019"
 - **Do NOT code as "error":**
"on [grammatical error: "the" missing] 12th of October"; "on the 12 [spelling error: "th" missing] of October"; "on the 12th October [grammatical error: "of" missing]"

Examples:

There are some more critereas i would like to say [incorrect plural form]

You was asking if you can do anything for me and i said no [incorrect verb number]

Which room have the best atmosphere? [omission of third person singular -s]

Which room have the best atmosphere? [incorrect verb number]

the room costs maximum 1500 francs [incorrect aspect]

and what about showing videos? is that working? [incorrect aspect]

In which room can i make also private speaks [word misorder]

I need room for 150 Persons [incorrect use of a/an]

Have you got a chance to do an presentation in the Alpha room? [incorrect use of a/an]

How much does the room Alpha cost? [superfluous article]

Do they have a beamer in? [superfluous word]

	<p>The <u>should</u> have space for [...] [omission of a word - "room"]</p> <p>How much space <u>has</u> it? [omission of dummy <i>do</i> in interrogative]</p>
<p>COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Errors\Spelling</p>	<p>Definition: This code is assigned to words containing orthographic errors including 'mechanical' typing errors but excluding punctuation errors (e.g., omission of end-of-sentence period, omission of apostrophe) and capitalization errors (e.g., omission of capitalization at the beginning of a turn, omission of capitalization of names).</p> <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Code the individual word that contains a spelling error. • When the same word contains more than one spelling error, assign one code only. • Also code spelling deviations when used for emphasis, e.g., "yesss!". • When a lexical item contains a lexical error as well as a spelling and/or grammatical error, assign error code "lexis" only, e.g. "Can we <u>made</u> a Presentation [lexical error/not coded for "grammar"]". • When a word contains a spelling error as well as a grammatical error, code both error types, e.g., "The <u>12</u> [spelling error ("th" missing)] <u>octobre</u> [spelling error ("octob<u>re</u>") and grammatical error ("of" missing)] 2019". <p>Examples:</p> <p>how much does <u>tis</u> room cost?</p> <p><u>Than</u> its just the room</p> <p><u>okey</u> which room is the best for a good <u>athmosphere</u></p> <p>what about the atmosphere in <u>thisroom</u></p>
<p>COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Errors\Lexis</p>	<p>Definition: This code is assigned to deviations in the use of lexical items. Deviations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • formal errors (e.g., misselection of suffixes or prepositions or pronouns, invention of non-existing words) • semantic errors (i.e., the choice of a lexical item in a context where its meaning is inappropriate or inaccurate)

- the use of German

Coding guidelines:

- Assign the code to the lexical item (i.e., word or phrase) that would need to be replaced in order to correct the utterance with minimal changes (e.g., "for 150 people to stay in", "which room is the best for a good atmosphere", "Does it have material").
- When a lexical item contains a lexical error as well as a spelling and/or grammatical error, assign error code "lexis" only, e.g. "Can we made a Presentation [lexical error/not coded for "grammar"]"
- When the same error is made more than once by the same student, code it each time.

Do NOT code as "error":

- "I'm searching for a room"
- "wanna", "gonna" etc.
- "1500_-" (considered a punctuation error, which is not coded)
- "It must be possible to..."
- "do a presentation" (but: code "make a presentation" as "error")
- "I take room Alpha"
- "play video and audio"

Examples:

Hello, i want to reservate a room an need your help [misselection of suffix]

we would like to come at the 12 june and then staying 5 days there [misselection of preposition]

Is it like very extra? [invention of non-existing word]

I'm searching for a room which [misselection of pronoun] 150 people can stay in [semantic error]

It is possible to remove the decorations and put somthing new [semantic error] of the year 2000 [semantic error]?

it must be posible to make a presentation [semantic error]

Hä [use of German]

and what about having apero? [use of German]

COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Clauses

Definition: The code is assigned to independent and subordinate clauses:

- An **independent clause** will be minimally a clause including a finite verb.
- A **subordinate clause** will consist minimally of a finite or non-finite verb element (e.g., "to" + infinitive, bare infinitive after a modal verb, participle after auxiliary verb) plus at least one other clause element (i.e., subject, object, complement, adverbial).

Coding guidelines:

- Only the learner's production is considered for coding.
- The code is assigned to the clause including punctuation marks.
- Utterances written entirely in German are excluded.
- The code is also assigned to erroneous constructions.

Examples:

Alright. [no verb – no clause] It is possible [clause 1] to remove the decorations [clause 2] and put something new of the year 2000? [clause 3]

So I would [clause 1] like [non-finite verb with no other clause element – no clause] to book the room alpha ["to"-infinitive with complement – clause 2].

yes, [no verb – no clause] but I need [clause 1] to know ["to" + infinitive with no other clause element – no clause] how much a room costs [clause 3]

i don't [clause 1] wan [bare infinitive after a modal verb with no other clause element – no clause] na pay more than 1500.- [clause 3]

thank you, [clause 1] see you. [clause 2] Goodbye [no verb – no clause]

no, [no verb – no clause] which room is the best [clause 1] for have also place for tidy conversation [erroneous "to"-infinitive with complement – clause 2]

i want [clause 1] to book the room gamma [clause 2]

COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Clauses\Error-free	Definition: An error-free clause.
	Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the clause including punctuation marks.
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Clauses\With error	Definition: A clause that contains one or more errors.
	Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the clause including punctuation marks.
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\AS-units	<p>Definition: A single interactant's utterance consisting of an independent clause, or sub-clausal unit, together with any subordinate clause(s) associated with either.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An independent clause will be minimally a clause including a finite verb. • An independent sub-clausal unit will consist of: either one or more phrases which can be elaborated to a full clause by means of recovery of ellipped elements from the context of the discourse or situation or a minor utterance (e.g., "thank you", "yes"). • A subordinate clause will consist minimally of a finite or non-finite verb element plus at least one other clause element (subject, object, complement or adverbial). <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only the learner's production is considered for coding. • The code is assigned to the AS-unit including punctuation marks. • Utterances written in German are excluded. • Coordinated elements (i.e., phrases or clauses connected with a coordinator such as "and", "or", "but") are considered to belong to the same AS-unit, unless they are separated by punctuation (comma, period) or a new message. <p>Examples:</p> <p><u>About 150 or more</u> [AS-unit 1]</p> <p><u>No,</u> [AS-unit 1] <u>this is it.</u> [AS-unit 2] <u>Thank you.</u> [AS-unit 3] <u>We'll be there at 8 am and the event will start at 9 am.</u> [AS-unit 4]</p> <p><u>thank you,</u> [AS-unit 1] <u>see you.</u> [AS-unit 2] <u>Goodbye</u> [AS-unit 3]</p> <p><u>Yes</u> [AS-unit 1] <u>sure,</u> [AS-unit 2] <u>I would like to book a room for minimum 150 people in your hotel.</u> [AS-unit 3] <u>The room should let us do a presentation and also meeting for small groups.</u> [AS-unit 4] <u>It</u></p>

should also have a good atmosphere. [AS-unit 5] It should make the guests happy. [AS-unit 6] Do you have room for maximum 1500 Franks? [AS-unit 7]

COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\AS-units\Error-free

Definition: An error-free AS-unit.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the AS-unit including punctuation marks.

COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\AS-units\With error

Definition: An AS-unit that contains one or more errors.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the AS-unit including punctuation marks.

COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests

Definition: A directive speech act that has the function to get the interlocutor to do something for the learner.

A request is composed of a head act and support moves that occur within the **head act** (i.e., internal modifiers) or before/after the head act (i.e., external modifiers).

Internal modifiers are lexical and syntactic elements within the head act that serve to mitigate the illocutionary force of a request.

External modifiers refer to utterances that are peripheral to the head act and also serve to mitigate its illocutionary force.

External modifiers are only considered if they are part of the same turn as the head act. **Turn** is defined here as a transfer of the 'floor' from one interlocutor to the other. A turn may consist of a single chat message or a sequence of messages by the same interlocutor (i.e., split turn). A message sequence that is interrupted by a message sent by the interlocutor resulting in an overlap is not considered as separate turns but part of the same split turn.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire request including head act and external modifiers, but excluding end-of-request punctuation marks.

Examples:

Ok, we'll go with room beta. Thanks for your advise. [request]

Not quite sure. The room should be able to fit up to 150 people. [request 1] We need a big screen so every one of said 150 people is able to see the presentation our "higher ups" made. [request 2] Our

	<p><u>workers should have the ability to chat with each other in small groups.</u> [request 3] <u>We need the room to give us a nice and fun atmosphere.</u> [request 4] <u>It should make a big impression on our guests, but shouldn't come off as "too exaggerated".</u> [request 5] <u>We're willing to pay 1'500 under these conditions.</u> [no request] <u>Is there a room you could suggest for us?</u> [request 6]</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy	<p>Definition: The type of strategy used for the linguistic realization of the request head act.</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Direct expression	<p>Definition: A request strategy resulting in a request with a high level of directness, where the head act contains syntactic markings such as grammatical mood (e.g., imperative) or an explicit performative verb.</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Direct expression\Imperative	<p>Definition: The grammatical mood of the verb in the utterance marks its illocutionary force as a request.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: <u>WAIT</u></p> <p>User: <u>Please give me an answer to my question.</u></p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Direct expression\Direct question	<p>Definition: Typically a request for information that is conveyed by a direct question.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>Bot: Room Gamma has two moveable monitors and speakers. User: <u>Perfect</u> [agree]. <u>How much does it cost?</u> [direct question]</p> <p>Bot: Gamma has two big portable screens and loudspeakers. User: <u>is it possible to communicate in small groups?</u> [direct question]</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Direct expression\Elliptical question	<p>Definition: Typically a request for information that is conveyed by an elliptical question, i.e., an interrogative that lacks a verb and/or subject which can be recovered from the context.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p>

Examples:

Bot: Room Gamma costs CHF 1100.

User: And the Beta Room? [elliptical question]

Bot: So sorry, I could not understand your last message. Could you please say it again?

User: First name? [elliptical question]

User: and what about having apero? [elliptical question]

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\Request
strategy\Direct expression\Indirect question

Definition: Typically a request for information that is conveyed by an indirect question, i.e., a question conveyed by a subordinate interrogative.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.

Examples:

Bot: Excuse me, could you rephrase this please?

User: I asked, if this is the "One King Hotel" in Toronto [indirect question].

User: yes [agreer], but I need to know how much a room costs [indirect question]

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\Request
strategy\Direct expression\Want statement

Definition: The learner expresses his or her desire that the action expressed in the request be carried out by the interlocutor.

Coding guidelines:

- The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.
- The code is only assigned when the learner wants the interlocutor to carry out the action, otherwise the code "strong hint" is assigned, e.g., "I don't wanna pay more than 1500.-" [strong hint]; "I would like to book a room for minimum 150 people in your hotel" [strong hint].

Examples:

Bot: The price is CHF 1100 CHF for room Gamma.

User: Great! [agreer] Then we would like to book the Gamma room. [want statement]

Bot: Room Gamma costs CHF 1100.

	User: <u>i would like to reserve the room Alpha</u> [want statement]
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Direct expression\Assertion	<p>Definition: The learner expresses his or her reservation request as a declarative statement.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p> <p>Example: Bot: Room Gamma is a spacious room with round tables for about 6-8 guests each. If you wish, the tables can be moved around. [User: Very nice [agreer], <u>I book the room Gamma for the october 12th</u> [assertion]</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Indirect expression	<p>Definition: A request strategy resulting in an indirect request, where the head act contains formulaic references to preconditions (e.g. could you do it) or relies on inferencing from contextual clues, as in hints (e.g. It's cold in here.).</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Indirect expression\Reference to preparatory conditions	<p>Definition: The utterance contains reference to a preparatory condition for the feasibility of the request such as the interlocutor's ability or willingness or the possibility to perform the action.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p> <p>Example: Bot: You can easily reach us by subway from the None. User: <u>can you tell me about the Alpha, Beta, Gamma rooms</u> [reference to preparatory conditions]?</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Request strategy\Indirect expression\Strong hint	<p>Definition: A statement that contains implicit reference to the action without explicitly stating the intended action.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the head act excluding punctuation marks.</p> <p>Examples: Bot: I will be happy to assist you. How can I help? User: <u>I am searching a room for 150 people</u> [strong hint].</p>

	<p>Bot: Room Gamma has two large screens and loudspeakers. The screens can be moved around. User: <u>i don't wanna pay more than 1500.-</u> [strong hint]</p> <p>Bot: The Gamma room can fit up to 200 people. User: <u>it must be possible to make a presentation</u> [strong hint]</p> <p>Bot: Alpha is equipped with a state-of-the-art multimedia set including a big screen, projector and sound system. User: <u>I am very intresed in the room Alpha</u> [strong hint]</p> <p>Bot: I will be happy to assist you. How can I help? User: <u>I need a room for about 150 persones</u> [strong hint]</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Internal modifier	<p>Definition: A lexical or syntactic element within the head act of a request that mitigates its illocutionary force.</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Internal modifier\Politeness marker	<p>Definition: An optional element added to the head act to bid for cooperative behavior.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <p>User: Could you <u>please</u> tell me prices of the rooms?</p> <p>User: Thank you for your passion, I'd like to take the Room Gamma for CHF 1100 with the two big portable screens and loudspeakers, for the 12 Oktober 2019. The reservation is under the Name Corti. <u>If it's possible</u>, and i'm sorry for the miss understanding, I hope you have a great day.</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\Internal modifier\Modal preterite	<p>Definition: The verb of the head act is modified by a modal in the preterite form.</p> <p>Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the modal verb.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>User: We <u>would</u> [modal preterite] like to book the room Alpha</p> <p>User: Okay [agreer] i <u>would</u> [modal preterite] like to book this one [head act – want statement]</p>
COMPLEXITY AND ACCURACY\Requests\External modifier	<p>Definition: A linguistic element before and/or after the head act of a request that mitigates its illocutionary force.</p>

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\External modifier\Alerter

Definition: A linguistic device preceding the head act that is used to get the interlocutor's attention.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the external modifier excluding punctuation. The code is only assigned if the modifier occurs in the same turn as the head act.

Example:

User: Hello [alerter], is this the One King Hotel in Toronto?

User: I have a question [alerter] is the room great for communication in little groups?

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\External
modifier\Grounder

Definition: An utterance in which the learner states his or her reasons or justifications for making the request.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the external modifier excluding punctuation. The code is only assigned if the modifier occurs in the same turn as the head act.

Example:

User: Okey [agreer] the room Alpha would fit our expectations [grounder], is the room free on 12th October 2019? [head act – direct question]

User: So i'm organizing an event for our Enterprise [grounder] and I'm looking for a room to book at your hotel [head act – strong hint].

User: I have questions about your hotel [grounder]. Did you have a room for 150 persons [head act – direct question]?

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\External modifier\Agreer

Definition: The learner expresses that he or she is satisfied with the offering.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the external modifier excluding punctuation marks. The code is only assigned if the modifier occurs in the same turn as the head act.

Examples:

Bot: All our rooms are below the price of 1500 Fr.

User: Yes [agreer], I would like to have the Gamma room [head act – want statement]

Bot: Room Gamma is a spacious room with tables for up to eight people. All the furniture can be moved.

User: That sounds great [agreer]. Is the room gamma fancy or like a normal room [head act – direct question]

Bot: Could you tell me which room you are interested in?

User: Both [agreer]. Do they have a beamer in [head act – direct question] ?

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\External
modifier\Appreciator

Definition: The learner expresses his or her gratitude for the (anticipated) performance of the action.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the external modifier excluding punctuation. The code is only assigned if the modifier occurs in the same turn as the head act.

Examples:

Bot: Room Gamma has two large screens and loudspeakers. The screens can be moved around.

User: Thanks [appreciator] and how is the atmosphere in the Room Gamma? [head act – direct question]

Bot: The outdoor section in room Beta offers a great view over the whole city. The indoor area has modern furnishing and a lot of natural light from the glass roof.

User: Ok [agreer], we'll go with room beta [head act – assertion]. Thanks for your advise [appreciator].

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\External
modifier\Disagreer

Definition: The learner expresses that he or she is dissatisfied.

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the external modifier excluding punctuation marks. The code is only assigned if the modifier occurs in the same turn as the head act.

Example:

Bot: Would you like me to book room None for the None?

User: no [disagreer], which room is the best for have also place for tidy conversation [head act – direct question]

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\Appropriateness

Definition: The pragmatic appropriateness of the request production.

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\Appropriateness\Inappropriate

Definition: A request is rated as “inappropriate” when one or more of the following criteria are met:

- the expressions are more direct or indirect than the situation requires
- internal and external modification is insufficient or infelicitous
- grammatical (i.e., grammar, vocabulary, spelling) and/or discourse (i.e., cohesive issues such as abrupt topic switches or unclear reference, insufficient detail, issues in the segmenting of sentences) errors seriously impede appropriateness

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire request including head act and external modifier.

Examples:

User: i'm looking for a room which i can make a presentation and who looks good

Bot: All of the three rooms are equipped for presentations.

Bot: Room Alpha offers a stage, state-of-the-art equipment including a large screen, a projector and dolby sound system.

Bot: Room Beta can be equipped with a moveable screen, projector, and loudspeakers.

Bot: Room Gamma has two large screens and loudspeakers. The screens can be moved around.

User: i don't wanna pay more than 1500.- [indirect request strategy inappropriate resp. insufficient modification, unclear reference/cohesion]

Bot: The price for Gamma is 1100 CHF.

User: Witsh size? [direct request strategy inappropriate, unclear reference]

User: okey which room is the best for a good atmosphere

Bot: Yes, sure.

Bot: Yes, certainly.

User: In which room can i make also private speaks [unclear cohesion, grammatical errors seriously impede appropriateness]

Bot: The outdoor section in room Beta offers a great view over the whole city. The indoor area has modern furnishing and a lot of natural light from the glass roof.

User: the room costs maximum 1500 francs [indirect request strategy inappropriate resp. insufficient modification, grammatical errors seriously impede appropriateness]

Bot: Yes, absolutely.
 Bot: Could you please tell me which room you are referring to?
 User: Which room have the best atmosphere? [unclear cohesion/abrupt topic change]

Bot: Could you please tell me your name?
 User: Chiara Kälin
 Bot: I am afraid I have trouble understanding. Please could you rephrase?
 User: How those the rooms cost? [abrupt topic change, grammatical errors seriously impede appropriateness]

Bot: For what date would you like to reserve room Alpha?
 User: but how much is it? [direct request strategy inappropriate, unclear cohesion/abrupt topic change]

Bot: There is space for 200 people in room Gamma.
 User: How about presentations [insufficient modification, direct request strategy/elliptical question inappropriate]

Bot: So, I will book room Gamma on the 13 of July 2020 for you. Could you please confirm if you would like me to proceed?
 User: per mail or like what [direct request strategy/elliptical question inappropriate, insufficient modification]

User: Are there any restaurants at the hotel?
 Bot: From the station you can easily reach us by foot.
 User: Food? [direct request strategy/elliptical question inappropriate, insufficient modification, unclear cohesion]

User: i need a room for 150 people
 Bot: There are three rooms available for 150 people.
 Bot: What information can I help you with?
 User: tell me more about Beta [direct request strategy inappropriate resp. insufficient modification]

COMPLEXITY AND
 ACCURACY\Requests\Appropriateness\Partly
 appropriate

Definition: A request is rated as “partly appropriate” when all of the following criteria are met:

- the expressions are at the level of directness that the situation requires

- internal and external modification is mostly sufficient and felicitous
- grammatical (i.e., grammar, vocabulary, spelling) and/or discourse (i.e., unclear cohesive issues such as abrupt topic switches or unclear reference, insufficient detail, issues in the segmenting of sentences) errors are noticeable and they interfere with appropriateness moderately

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire request including head act and external modifier.

Examples:

User: Hello my name is Jessica and i'm working for the company Coop

Bot: Thank you for contacting One King Hotel, Jessica. I will gladly assist you in finding a room.

Bot: How can I help you?

User: I'm searching for a room which 150 people can stay in [grammatical errors are noticeable and partly interfere with appropriateness moderately]

Bot: Yes, sure.

Bot: Yes, certainly.

User: In which room can i make also private speaks [inappropriate]

Bot: I am sorry, I did not understand that. Could you please try one more time?

User: which room has the most place to have conversations [partly appropriate: grammatical errors are noticeable and interfere with appropriateness moderately]

Bot: Room Gamma is a spacious room with round tables for about 6-8 guests each. If you wish, the tables can be moved around.

User: it must be a good vibe in the room for the people [grammatical and cohesive issues are noticeable and interfere with appropriateness moderately, modification somewhat insufficient/infelicitous]

Bot: Thank you, the room has just been booked.

Bot: Is there anything else I can do for you?

User: i want to book the room gamma [modification somewhat insufficient, cohesive issue interferes with appropriateness moderately]

Bot: I will be happy to assist you. How can I help?

User: I am searching a room for 150 people [modification somewhat insufficient]

COMPLEXITY AND
ACCURACY\Requests\Appropriateness\Fully
appropriate

Definition: A request is rated as “fully appropriate” when all of the following criteria are met:

- the expressions are at the level of directness that the situation requires
- internal and external modification is sufficient and felicitous
- no or almost no grammatical (i.e., grammar, vocabulary, spelling) and/or discourse (i.e., cohesive issues such as abrupt topic switches or unclear reference, insufficient detail, issues in the segmenting of sentences) errors that do not interfere with appropriateness

Coding guideline: The code is assigned to the entire request including head act and external modifier.

Examples:

Bot: Room Alpha is a spacious auditorium on the basement floor with comfortable seating and a stage. It is equipped with multimedia facilities and a lighting system.

Bot: Beta has a modern touch. It is located on the 15th floor and offers incredible views. The glass roof brings in natural light and creates a beautiful atmosphere.

Bot: Room Gamma has the original decoration from the 1920s which gives the room an elegant look.

User: Could you please tell me prices of the rooms? [modification sufficient and felicitous, appropriate level of directness, no errors]

Bot: Alpha is equipped with a state-of-the-art multimedia set including a big screen, projector and sound system.

User: I am very intresed in the room Alpha [indirect request strategy appropriate/does not need modification, grammatical errors do not impede appropriateness]

Bot: There are two rooms available for 150 people.

Bot: Room Alpha has space for up to 270 people.

Bot: Room Gamma has space for 200 people.

User: Which one is the better one or which do you prefer? [direct request strategy appropriate/does not need modification, no errors]

User: Hello

Bot: Thank you for contacting One King Hotel. I will gladly assist you in finding a room.

Bot: I will be happy to assist you. How can I help?

User: My name is Arta Berisha and I'm an apprentice for Sanitas Health Insurance. We got a big event planned for the 12th of October 2019 and we need a room for this event to take place in.

[indirect request strategy appropriate, sufficient/felicitous modification, minor errors do not impede appropriateness]

Bot: Room Gamma is decorated in the original 1920s stlye. It is located on the first floor of the hotel.

User: Okey thanks for all your information. Could you do a reservation for me? [direct request strategy appropriate, sufficient/felicitous modification, minor errors do not impede appropriateness]

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Task completion

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Task completion\Successful

Definition: A room is booked after all five of the required information pieces on at least one of the rooms have been requested and answered in sufficient detail and accurately processed.

Required information:

- capacity
- audio/video equipment
- setup for small groups
- looks/ambiance
- cost

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Task completion\Partly successful

Definition: A room is booked after three or four pieces of the required information pieces on at least one of the rooms have been requested and answered in sufficient detail and accurately processed.

Required information:

- capacity
- audio/video equipment
- setup for small groups
- looks/ambiance
- cost

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Task completion\Not successful	<p>Definition: This code is assigned when at least one of the following criteria is met:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No room is booked. • Only two or less of the required information pieces are requested and answered. • Three or more of the received information pieces are inaccurately processed. <p>Required information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capacity • audio/video equipment • setup for small groups • looks/ambiance • cost <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.</p>
COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic structure	<p>Definition: The learner follows the generic structure in the following order throughout.</p> <p>Generic structure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. greeting 2. self-presentation (name, position) and/or presentation of reason for contact 3. decision stage: information requests and provision 4. reservation request 5. reservation closure 6. leave-taking <p>Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.</p>
COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic structure\Partly genre-appropriate	<p>Definition: The learner follows the generic structure in the following order with one or two deviations.</p> <p>Generic structure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. greeting 2. self-presentation (name, position) and/or presentation of reason for contact 3. decision stage: information requests and provision 4. reservation request 5. reservation closure

6. leave-taking

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic structure\Inappropriate

Definition: The learner follows the generic structure in the following order with more than two deviations.

Generic structure:

1. greeting
2. self-presentation (name, position) and/or presentation of reason for contact
3. decision stage: information requests and provision
4. reservation request
5. reservation closure
6. leave-taking

Coding guideline: Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.

COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic style\Formal

Definition: A formal style is used consistently, i.e., in the majority of the utterances formal forms dominate.

Features of formal style:

- use of full rather than contracted forms (e.g., did not, will not rather than didn't, won't)
- use of full rather than elliptical clauses
- use of punctuation
- use of written out forms rather than abbreviations (e.g., persons, October rather than pers., Oct.)
- requests (requests for information are not considered): use of indirect form (e.g., I would be grateful if you could), modal preterites (e.g., would like), politeness markers (e.g., please) formal forms of greeting and leave-taking (e.g., Dear, Kind regards, Many thanks)

Coding guidelines:

- Procedure:
 - 1. Assess for each utterance separately the level of style (i.e., informal, mixed, formal).
 - 2. Add up the total of informal, mixed, and formal utterances.
 - 3. Deduct overall style:
 - majority of utterances are informal = rate interaction as "informal"
 - majority of utterances are formal = rate interaction as "formal"

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ majority of utterances are mixed = rate interaction as “mixed” ▪ equal number of informal and formal utterances (+/- 1) = rate interaction as “mixed” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.
<p>COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic style\Mixed</p>	<p>Definition: Formal and informal styles are balanced, i.e., in the majority of the utterances both formal and informal forms are used rather than predominantly formal or informal or there is an equal number of utterances with formal and informal forms.</p> <p>Features of formal style:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use of full rather than contracted forms (e.g., did not, will not rather than didn't, won't) • use of full rather than elliptical clauses • use of punctuation • use of written out forms rather than abbreviations (e.g., persons, October rather than pers., Oct.) • requests (requests for information are not considered): use of indirect form (e.g., I would be grateful if you could), modal preterites (e.g., would like), politeness markers (e.g., please) formal forms of greeting and leave-taking (e.g., Dear, Kind regards, Many thanks) <p>Coding guidelines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procedure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 1. Assess for each utterance separately the level of style (i.e., informal, mixed, formal). ○ 2. Add up the total of informal, mixed, and formal utterances. ○ 3. Deduct overall style: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ majority of utterances are informal = rate interaction as “informal” ▪ majority of utterances are formal = rate interaction as “formal” ▪ majority of utterances are mixed = rate interaction as “mixed” ▪ equal number of informal and formal utterances (+/- 1) = rate interaction as “mixed” • Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.
<p>COMMUNICATIVE ADEQUACY\Generic style\Informal</p>	<p>Definition: An informal style is used consistently, i.e., in the majority of the utterances informal forms dominate.</p> <p>Features of formal style:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use of full rather than contracted forms (e.g., did not, will not rather than didn't, won't)

- use of full rather than elliptical clauses
- use of punctuation
- use of written out forms rather than abbreviations (e.g., persons, October rather than pers., Oct.)
- requests (requests for information are not considered): use of indirect form (e.g., I would be grateful if you could), modal preterites (e.g., would like), politeness markers (e.g., please) formal forms of greeting and leave-taking (e.g., Dear, Kind regards, Many thanks)

Coding guidelines:

- Procedure:
 - 1. Assess for each utterance separately the level of style (i.e., informal, mixed, formal).
 - 2. Add up the total of informal, mixed, and formal utterances.
 - 3. Deduct overall style:
 - majority of utterances are informal = rate interaction as “informal”
 - majority of utterances are formal = rate interaction as “formal”
 - majority of utterances are mixed = rate interaction as “mixed”
 - equal number of informal and formal utterances (+/- 1) = rate interaction as “mixed”
- Assign the code to the final line of the script including timestamp.